

Compressive Fatigue Damage Accumulation near Holes in Graphite/Epoxy Laminates

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ABSTRACT

Initiation and propagation of compression - compression fatigue damage near 1.25 cm diameter holes in AS/3501-6 graphite/epoxy laminates were experimentally investigated. 178 30.5 x 5.0 cm specimens of four different layups were subjected to 19 HZ, R = 10 fatigue cycling. Most tests were conducted using ($\pm 45/0$)_s laminates. Tests of a smaller number of (0/ ± 45)_s, (0/ ± 30)_s and ($\pm 30/0$)_s laminates were conducted to study the influence of stacking sequence and ply orientation. Out-of-plane Moire interferometry was used to observe damage propagation during the test program. Fatigue damage growth in each specimen was quantified by plotting the area enclosed by the outermost Moire fringe line measured from a chronological succession of damage photographs. The shape of these damage area versus cycle curves was relatively consistent for specimens with the same layup, but varied considerably for different laminate types. In most cases fatigue failure was preceded by a rapid increase in the rate of damage accumulation. The time to first observable damage, site of damage initiation, the surface patterns formed by the damage as it grew, and life to fatigue failure were all found to be influenced by stacking sequence and ply orientation. When tested at peak compressive loads lower than 56% of its net section static strength, no fatigue damage was detected in ($\pm 45/0$)_s specimens.

INTRODUCTION

The application of cyclic loads to a structural component generally results in local damage prior to catastrophic failure. Metals are affected only by cyclic tensile loads. Ryder and Walker (1) have shown that laminated composites are most sensitive to the presence of compressive loads in the fatigue spectrum. In laminates containing some angle plies, interply delamination has been found to be the dominant mode of fatigue damage propagation (2-4).

This paper presents results of an experimental study of damage initiation and propagation near holes in graphite/epoxy laminates subjected to compression - compression fatigue. While this type of data is vital for damage tolerant design and the establishment of realistic composite aircraft

inspection intervals, information on the pre-failure fatigue behavior of composites has to date been relatively scarce. This work was intended to provide a statistically significant data base for future analytical and experimental investigations.

PROCEDURE

Test Specimen Fabrication

Axially loaded sandwich column specimens of the type shown in Figure 1 were used in this test program. Five 30.5 x 5.0 cm Hercules AS1/5208-6 graphite/epoxy face sheets were cut from each of the forty four 30.5 x 30.5 cm plates fabricated for this project. A standardized 177°C, 690 KPa autoclave curing cycle developed by the Massachusetts Institute of Technology's Technology Laboratory for Advanced Composites (4) was employed. After drilling a centrally located 1.25 cm hole in each coupon, the sandwich was assembled and bonded using American Cyanamid FM-123 film adhesive. FM-37-2 foaming adhesive was used to join the 2.5 cm thick, 72 and 354 kg/m³ aluminum honeycomb core peices during this operation. 7.5 x 6.25 cm (0₂/90₂) fiberglass loading tabs were attached separately. Diamond coated tools were used for all cutting and drilling operations.

FIGURE 1 SANDWICH COLUMN TEST SPECIMEN

Sandwich specimens were employed as a means of stabilizing the 0.8 mm thick graphite/epoxy laminates during the application of compressive load. This eliminated the need for external supports that would have interfered with the observation of fatigue damage. Static compressive tests using specimens with back to back strain gages confirmed that buckling was completely eliminated at loads lower than the static compression strength of the laminate.

Observation of Fatigue Damage

The nondestructive inspection method employed in this program, out-of-plane Moire interferometry, allowed the real time observation of fatigue damage initiation and propagation. Delamination, the dominant form of fatigue damage in angle ply laminates, produced local specimen thickness changes. The out-of-plane Moire technique, described more completely in

reference 5, was used to measure these thickness changes and delineate areas of subsurface damage. Comparison of Moire patterns observed on damaged specimens and microscopically examined cross sections cut from their laminates revealed that the perimeter of delaminated zones was identified to within ± 3 mm.

Test Method

Tests were conducted using a 44.5 KN Material Test Systems Model 810 testing machine operated in the 44.5 KN range. Specimens were held in MTS hydraulic grips adjusted to apply a 2.07 to 3.45 MPa normal load to the loading tabs. Specimens of the type shown in Figure 1 were used for both static and fatigue testing. All fatigue testing, along with most static testing, was performed in the load controlled mode. A few stroke controlled static tests were used to establish the net section strength of each of the four laminate types tested. When possible, load was released after failure of just one graphite/epoxy column face.

Fatigue loads were chosen to span the range between static failure and the fatigue limit with a fairly uniform distribution of data points. Testing was performed at 19 HZ to eliminate a hydraulic system resonance that was observed when tests were conducted at 20 HZ. Loading was periodically halted for between 2 and 5 seconds to permit photographs of developing Moire patterns to be taken. A static force of slightly more than half the maximum compressive load was maintained during this period. The increment between successive pictures was varied in 8 stages from 200 to 20000 cycles.

If fracture did not occur by 600,000 cycles, standard procedure was to immediately conduct a residual strength test by gradually increasing compressive load until static failure was induced. Fatigue loading of a few specimens was extended beyond this point, with two specimens tested to one million cycles. Ten specimens were removed from the testing machine prior to fatigue failure. Microscopic examination of cross sections taken near the edge of the hole allowed comparison of Moire patterns with actual laminate damage.

RESULTS

Static Tests

Table 1 lists average static compression strength and modulus values for the four laminate types tested during this program. Calculated strength values were biased by the fact that failure of the weaker sandwich face makes the strength of the stronger face unmeasurable. It is interesting to note that the compressive strength of the two laminates containing $\pm 30^\circ$ plies was found to be lower than the two $\pm 45^\circ$ laminates. Similar findings have been reported by Graves (6).

Table 1. Average Static Values

Laminate Type	Net Section Compressive Ultimate (MPa)	Standard Deviation (MPa)	E Laminate Modulus (GPa)	Standard Deviation (MPa)	Laminate Theory (GPa)
($\pm 45/0$) _s	455.3	40.4	54.6	2.2	54.1
(0/ ± 45) _s	453.4	30.9	57.2	4.3	54.1
($\pm 30/0$) _s	425.5	29.3	82.1	5.9	75.8
(0/ ± 30) _s	402.3	4.5	80.8	0.5	75.8

Fracture of laminates was often preceded by cracking sounds initiating near 90% of the ultimate load. Following these audible indications of damage, small delaminated zones were sometimes observed near the hole. The

size of the observed prefailure damage in static tests was much smaller than the critical damage area typical of the fatigue results.

Fatigue Life

Fatigue life data has been plotted in Figure 2. Data points for 21 failed and 26 unfailed ($\pm 45/0$)_s specimens are presented. No fatigue failures of this laminate type were observed for tests conducted at peak compression loads less than 65% of the average static strength. Two samples survived a total of one million fatigue cycles. Most tests, however, were stopped if failure had not occurred by 600,000 cycles, and a residual strength test immediately conducted. The average of 18 ($\pm 45/0$)_s residual strength measurements was 7% lower than this laminate's virgin static strength.

FIGURE 2 NET SECTION STRESS VERSUS CYCLES TO FAILURE

The three (0/ ± 45)_s fatigue failures in Figure 2 show that moving the $\pm 45^\circ$ plies to the interior of the laminate caused nearly an order of magnitude reduction in fatigue life. Compare, for example, the 6040 cycle life of the (0/ ± 45)_s specimen tested at 323.6 MPa with the 39,600 cycles sustained by the shortest lived of the ($\pm 45/0$)_s specimens tested in this load range. No similar stacking sequence effect can be discerned in the failure data for the (0/ ± 30)_s and ($\pm 30/0$)_s specimens. Failures for both these laminates occurred at load levels below the apparent fatigue limit of the ($\pm 45/0$)_s specimens.

Damage Initiation

Life to first observable damage has been plotted in Figure 3. Closed symbols in this figure represent the first sign of fatigue damage in negatives of Moire pattern photographs examined under 10 power magnification. Open symbols indicate specimens that survived fatigue loading with no apparent damage. Comparison of time to damage initiation in this figure with life to failure in Figure 2 shows that a significant period of time could elapse between initiation of damage and final failure. No damage was observed in any ($\pm 45/0$)_s specimen tested at loads less than 56% of the laminate's average static strength.

Damage initiation data points for (0/ ± 45)_s specimens are located near the rapid initiation side of the ($\pm 45/0$)_s data. Recall that the stacking

sequence with 0° plies on the outside was shown to have a much shorter life to failure than the layup with $\pm 45^\circ$ outer plies when tested at the same load level. When the angle plies were placed at 30° , life to failure was not greatly affected by their location within the laminate. Figure 3, however, shows a significant difference in life to damage initiation. The $(0/\pm 30)_S$ stacking sequence showed signs of damage nearly an order of magnitude sooner than the $(\pm 30/0)_S$ layup.

FIGURE 3 NET SECTION STRESS VERSUS CYCLES TO FIRST DAMAGE

Figure 4 plots the location of initial damage for each of the four laminate types. Most of the $(\pm 45/0)_S$ specimens initiated damage within $\pm 10^\circ$ of one of the points on the holes edge displaced 45° from the load direction. The other three laminate types all showed the first sign of damage in the two 10° sectors located adjacent to and rotated counterclockwise from a perpendicular to the load direction.

FIGURE 4 DAMAGE INITIATION SITES

Damage Propagation

Approximately 10,000 individual photographs of developing damage were taken during this test program. As described in the previous section, these negatives were studied to locate the time of damage initiation. In addition, prints of up to sixteen selected frames of damage growth in each test specimen were made. A comprehensive set of these prints is available in Reference 5.

Figure 5 shows idealized sketches of typical damage growth photographs. Each individual drawing shows a region surrounding the 1.25 cm diameter hole in the laminate, along with representations of the Moire fringe lines observed after the number of fatigue cycles indicated near each frame. Each Moire fringe line represents a local 0.2 mm change in laminate thickness. Maximum sensitivity of the method was approximately 1/4 fringe, or 0.05 mm. Smooth contours represent subsurface delamination. Discontinuities in the fringes indicate cracks in the outer ply. The load direction in these sketches was from the top of the page.

Figure 5a shows damage growth in $(\pm 45/0)_S$ laminates. Damage in this type of layup often tended to initiate and grow in a four leaf clover pattern. This pattern usually was disturbed by the coalescence of two of its lobes or the formation of cracks prior to failure. The $(0/\pm 45)$ laminate of Figure 5b shows a much different pattern. Damage in these laminates initiated as delamination at the hole edge near the point of minimum net section, and propagated rapidly in the load direction. Large sections of the

FIGURE 5 TYPICAL PROGRESSION OF FATIGUE DAMAGE

load bearing 0° ply were rendered ineffective, explaining the much shorter fatigue life of this stacking sequence.

The $(\pm 30/0)_S$ specimen shown in Figure 5c developed localized regions of delamination which grew very slowly in a direction perpendicular to the load. Failure occurred with relatively little damage when compared to the other three laminates studied. The $(0/\pm 30)_S$ laminates shown in Figure 5d developed damage similar to that of the $(0/\pm 45)_S$ specimens. Propagation, however, proceeded as a series of stairstep delaminations in the outer 0° ply. This pattern usually traveled away from the hole at approximately a 30° angle, and sometimes reached the outer edge of the coupon without producing a failure.

Damage accumulation in each test specimen was quantified by plotting the area enclosed by the outermost Moire fringe line versus cycles. Each laminate type was found to have a characteristically shaped damage accumulation curve. Important features of these curves are indicated in Figure 6. Damage accumulated in most $(\pm 45/0)_S$ specimens at a gradually increasing rate, resulting in a smooth transition from slow growth early in a test to rapid growth prior to failure. $(0/\pm 45)_S$ began to rapidly accumulate damage immediately after initiation, and typically failed with comparatively small damage area.

$(\pm 30/0)_S$ specimens were unusual in that damage at first grew very slowly, then underwent a short period of extremely rapid propagation. Failure occurred in these specimens with very little accumulated damage. The damage growth curve for $(0/\pm 30)_S$ laminates was similar to the $(\pm 45/0)_S$'s, but exhibited a slightly sharper transition from slow to rapid growth. The stairstep nature of propagation in this laminate is reflected in its discontinuous damage growth curve.

FIGURE 6 IDEALIZED DAMAGE ACCUMULATION CURVES

SUMMARY

Stacking sequence and ply orientation were found to significantly affect the damage initiation and propagation behavior of graphite/epoxy laminates subjected to compression-compression fatigue. Placing 0° plies on the outside of laminates containing $\pm 45^\circ$'s reduced fatigue life by nearly an order of magnitude. When 30° angle plies were tested, the location of the 0° plies in the laminate had little influence on time to failure at the same load level. In this case, however, damage initiation occurred much sooner in the $(0/\pm 30)_S$ layup.

Each of the four laminate types had a differently shaped damage accumulation versus cycle curve. Two of the laminates tested, the ($\pm 45/0$)_s and ($0/\pm 30$)_s layups, initiated damage early and accumulated damage at a slowly increasing rate for much of their lives. Damage in the ($0/\pm 45$)_s laminates grew rapidly after a relatively early initiation, producing the shortest fatigue life of the four laminates tested. ($\pm 30/0$)_s specimens developed and accumulated damage very slowly, then underwent a period of rapid growth prior to failure. Damage area at failure for this laminate was the smallest of the layups tested.

The propagation of damage is an extremely important consideration in the design of fatigue critical structures. Inspection intervals for damage sensitive components have traditionally been established by time required for damage to grow from the minimum inspectable size to a size likely to induce failure. This work has shown that the improper choice of stacking sequence can result in uninspectable designs. Laminates with long periods of slow growth and relatively large damage area at failure, such as the ($\pm 45/0$)_s and ($0/\pm 30$)_s laminates of this program, are far more desirable than laminates which accumulate damage rapidly after a small region of slow growth.

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